
TRANSMISSION OF LANGUAGE AND CULTURE

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Annotatsiya. Til va madaniyatning o'tkazilishi deganda jamiyat yoki jamoada tillar va madaniy amaliyotlarning avloddan-avlodga o'tishi jarayoni tushuniladi. Bu uzatish turli vositalar, jumladan, rasmiy ta'lim, norasmiy o'zaro ta'sirlar, oila dinamikasi, ommaviy axborot vositalari va ijtimoiy institutlar orqali sodir bo'lishi mumkin.

Tilni uzatish muayyan tilning lug'at, grammatika va foydalanish qoidalarini o'rgatish va o'rganishni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu jarayon odatda erta bolalikdan oila muhitida boshlanadi va rasmiy ta'lim va ijtimoiy o'zaro munosabatlar orqali davom etadi. Tilni uzatish til xilma-xilligini saqlash va madaniy merosni saqlash uchun juda muhimdir.

Madaniy uzatish urf-odatlar, urf-odatlar, e'tiqodlar, qadriyatlar, marosimlar va normalarning avloddan-avlodga o'tishini o'z ichiga oladi. Bu jarayon ko'pincha tilni uzatish bilan bog'liq bo'ladi, chunki til madaniyatning asosiy jihati bo'lib,

madaniy o'ziga xoslikni ifodalash va davom ettirish vositasi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Madaniy uzatish turli kanallar, jumladan, oilaviy marosimlar, jamoat bayramlari, hikoyalar, diniy muassasalar va ommaviy axborot vositalari orqali amalga oshiriladi.

Til va madaniyatning samarali uzatilishi jamiyatlarning uzluksizligi va jipsligi uchun zarurdir. U jamoa a'zolarida o'ziga xoslik va o'ziga xoslik hissini uyg'otadi, avlodlar o'rtasidagi aloqalarni mustahkamlaydi va jamoaviy xotirani saqlaydi. Biroq, globallashuv, migratsiya, urbanizatsiya va texnologik taraqqiyot til va madaniyatni uzatish uchun imkoniyatlar va qiyinchiliklarni keltirib chiqaradi, chunki ular tildan foydalanish shakllari, madaniy amaliyotlar va o'zlikni shakllantirishga ta'sir qiladi.

Tilshunoslik, antropologiya, sotsiologiya va ta'lim kabi sohalardagi tadqiqotchilar jamiyatlar uzluksizlikni qanday saqlab turishi va o'zgaruvchan sharoitlarga moslashishini yaxshiroq tushunish uchun til va madaniyatni uzatish mexanizmlari va dinamikasini o'rganadilar. Ular avlodlararo muloqot shakllari, tilni jonlantirish harakatlari, madaniyatni qayta tiklash harakatlari va til va madaniyatni saqlashda texnologiyaning roli kabi uzatish jarayonlariga ta'sir qiluvchi omillarni o'rganadilar.

Kalit so'zlar Globallashuv, avlodlar o'rtasidagi aloqalar, An'ana, qadriyat, marosim

Аннотация. Передача языка и культуры относится к процессу, посредством которого языки и культурные обычаи передаются от одного поколения к другому внутри общества или сообщества. Эта передача может происходить различными способами, включая формальное образование, неформальное взаимодействие, семейную динамику, средства массовой информации и социальные институты.

Передача языка включает в себя преподавание и изучение словарного запаса, грамматики и правил использования конкретного языка. Этот процесс обычно начинается в раннем детстве в семейной среде и продолжается через формальное образование и социальные взаимодействия. Передача языка имеет решающее значение для поддержания языкового разнообразия и сохранения культурного наследия.

Культурная передача включает в себя передачу обычаев, традиций, верований, ценностей, ритуалов и норм от одного поколения к другому. Этот процесс часто переплетается с передачей языка, поскольку язык является фундаментальным аспектом культуры и служит средством выражения и сохранения культурной самобытности. Культурная передача происходит по различным каналам, включая семейные ритуалы, общественные праздники, рассказывание историй, религиозные институты и средства массовой информации.

Эффективная передача языка и культуры имеет важное значение для преемственности и сплоченности общества. Это способствует развитию чувства принадлежности и идентичности среди членов сообщества,

укрепляет связи между поколениями и сохраняет коллективную память. Однако глобализация, миграция, урбанизация и технологический прогресс создают как возможности, так и проблемы для передачи языка и культуры, поскольку они влияют на модели использования языка, культурные практики и формирование идентичности.

Исследователи в таких областях, как лингвистика, антропология, социология и образование, изучают механизмы и динамику языковой и культурной передачи, чтобы лучше понять, как общества сохраняют преемственность и адаптируются к меняющимся обстоятельствам. Они исследуют факторы, влияющие на процессы передачи, такие как модели общения между поколениями, усилия по возрождению языка, движения за возрождение культуры, а также роль технологий в сохранении языка и

Ключевые слова: Глобализация, связи между поколениями, Традиции, ценности, ритуалы

Annotation

Transmission of language and culture refers to the process by which languages and cultural practices are passed down from one generation to another within a society or community. This transmission can occur through various means, including formal education, informal interactions, family dynamics, media, and societal institutions.

Language transmission involves teaching and learning the vocabulary, grammar, and usage rules of a particular language. This process typically starts in early childhood within the family environment and continues through formal education and social interactions. Language transmission is crucial for maintaining linguistic diversity and preserving cultural heritage.

Cultural transmission encompasses the passing down of customs, traditions, beliefs, values, rituals, and norms from one generation to the next. This process is often intertwined with language transmission, as language is a fundamental aspect of culture and serves as a medium for expressing and perpetuating cultural identity. Cultural transmission occurs through various channels, including family rituals, community celebrations, storytelling, religious institutions, and media.

Effective transmission of language and culture is essential for the continuity and cohesion of societies. It fosters a sense of belonging and identity among community members, strengthens intergenerational bonds, and preserves collective memory. However, globalization, migration, urbanization, and technological advancements present both opportunities and challenges for the transmission of language and culture, as they influence patterns of language use, cultural practices, and identity formation.

Researchers in fields such as linguistics, anthropology, sociology, and education study the mechanisms and dynamics of language and cultural transmission to better understand how societies maintain continuity and adapt to changing circumstances. They explore factors influencing transmission processes, such as intergenerational

communication patterns, language revitalization efforts, cultural revitalization movements, and the role of technology in language and culture preservation.

Key words: Globalization , intergenerational bonds, Tradition, value, ritual

Introduction

Language is a crucial element of culture, defining culture as all aspects of human life influenced by society. While basic actions like eating are not cultural, the specific practices around food consumption constitute culture. Language, as a primary tool for communication, is seen as a cornerstone of cultural identity.

Although language acquisition and usage have innate components, individuals primarily learn language as part of their societal upbringing. Language and society are mutually dependent; language could only develop within social contexts, and societies rely on common languages for cohesion. Language acquisition mostly occurs through exposure to speech, with formal teaching playing a lesser role, particularly in first-language learning.

Moreover, culture, including its history, is largely conveyed through language. Unlike animals, whose behavior is relatively stable and instinct-driven, human cultures and languages exhibit significant diversity across time and geography. While animal behavior evolves slowly over time, human cultures can change rapidly, influenced by various factors such as technological advancements and social dynamics.

The transmission of language and culture involves the passing on of linguistic and societal norms, practices, and values from one generation to another within a community or society. Here are key points regarding the transmission of language and culture.¹

The transfer of language and culture involves the inheritance of linguistic and societal norms, customs, and principles from one generation to another within a community or society. Here are key facets concerning language and culture transmission:

1. **Cultural Immersion:** Children predominantly acquire their primary language by immersing themselves in their cultural environment, assimilating language through exposure to conversations, narratives, and interactions within their community.
2. **Grammar Formation:** Children frequently grasp language rules and structures through a process of "grammar formation," assembling these components from the language input they receive, rather than through explicit instruction.
3. **Parental Influence:** Parents and caregivers wield significant influence over language transmission by providing linguistic input, rectifying language errors, and broadening their children's vocabulary through everyday interactions.
4. **Socialization:** Language transmission is intertwined with broader socialization processes, wherein children learn not only language but also cultural norms, values, and behaviors from their families, peers, and community members.

¹ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/language/Language-and-culture>.

5. Formal Education: While informal language acquisition takes precedence, formal education systems also contribute to language transmission by imparting literacy skills, formal grammar, and aspects of linguistic standardization.
6. Language Instruction: In formal educational settings, language teaching often concentrates on second language acquisition or on aspects of literacy and language usage in students' native language.²
7. Cultural Conveyance: Language serves as a primary conduit for cultural conveyance, conveying the accumulated knowledge, traditions, beliefs, and practices of a community or society. Through language, cultural narratives, histories, and values are passed from one generation to another.
8. Interconnection: Language and culture are intricately interlinked, with language both reflecting and shaping cultural identity, social bonds, and collective memory. Language shifts often mirror broader cultural transformations, and vice versa.³

In essence, the transmission of language and culture is a dynamic and intricate process that occurs through a blend of informal social interactions, formal education, and cultural customs within communities and societies.⁴

Language is transmitted culturally; that is, it is *learned*. To a lesser extent it is taught, when parents, for example, deliberately encourage their children to talk

² George Yule, *The Study of Language*, 4th ed. Cambridge University Press, 2010

³ <https://study.com/academy/lesson/cultural-transmission-definition-theory.html#:~:text=Cultural%20transmission%20is%20the%20process,one%20example%20of%20cultural%20transmission>

⁴ James R. Hurford, "The Language Mosaic and Its Evolution." *Language Evolution*, ed. by Morten H. Christiansen and Simon Kirby. Oxford University Press, 2003

and to respond to talk, correct their mistakes, and enlarge their vocabulary. Human infants, growing up in isolation, produce no 'instinctive' language. Cultural transmission of a specific language is crucial in the human acquisition process. The evidence that human beings do indeed have species-unique modes of cultural transmission is overwhelming.⁵ Most importantly, the cultural traditions and artifacts of human beings accumulate modification over time in a way that those of other animal species do not—so-called cumulative cultural evolution. Cultural transmission theory asserts that cultural transmission is accomplished primarily through experiential learning. Experiential learning is how an individual learns about the culture around them. It is an immersive type of experience, where a person learns by being exposed to the culture and then mimicking what they see. This is similar to teach-back learning, where the individual learns a concept and then retains the information by putting the information in their own words. Experiential learning focuses on real-life experiences of culture; hands-on experiences form the backbone of this type of cultural phenomenon.⁶ "A basic dichotomy in language evolution is between the biological evolution of the language capacity and the historical evolution of individual languages, mediated by cultural transmission. The child is simultaneously learning the meanings associated with the culture, realized linguistically by the lexico-grammatical system of the language The child is simultaneously learning the meanings associated with the

⁵ 5. Halliday 1978: 23." Linda Thompson, "Learning Language: Learning Culture in Singapore." *Language, Education, and Discourse: Functional Approaches*, ed. by Joseph A. Foley. Continuum, 2004

⁶ <https://www.thoughtco.com/what-is-cultural-transmission-1689814>

culture, realized linguistically by the lexico-grammatical system of the language.⁷

Conclusion

In summary, the complex interconnection between culture and language is undeniable, with each exerting a profound influence on the other. This study has delved into how language serves as a mirror of cultural values, norms, and identity, while also acting as a conduit through which culture is conveyed and sustained. From the nuances of vocabulary to the intricacies of grammar, language encapsulates the essence of a culture, embodying its historical roots, beliefs, and societal frameworks.

Moreover, our analysis has underscored the fluid nature of this relationship, wherein cultural transformations can precipitate linguistic changes, and linguistic innovations can, in turn, impact cultural dynamics. Whether spurred by globalization, migration patterns, or technological advancements, cultures and languages undergo constant interaction and adaptation, resulting in a diverse and interconnected global landscape.

Recognizing the intricate interplay between culture and language holds

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7.<https://www.google.com/search?q=transmission+of+culture+and+language+information+from+books&sca>

significance not only for scholars in linguistics and anthropology but also for educators, policymakers, and individuals navigating a multicultural milieu. Embracing linguistic and cultural diversity fosters empathy, enhances communication, and promotes collaboration across diverse communities, thus contributing to a more inclusive and cohesive global society.

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